

Synthesis of some New Pyrazole and Pyrazolin-5-one Derivatives of Sulphonamides

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Manuscript received 17 January 1991, revised 17 June 1991,
accepted 26 June 1991

PYRAZOLES and pyrazolin-5-ones and a large number of their derivatives are biologically active compounds^{1,2}. An arylazo grouping is of importance in promoting antineoplastic activity^{2,3}. Keeping in view the biological importance of hydrazono group⁴, pyrazolin-5-ones, pyrazoles and arylazo group, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise some of these compounds as possible biologically active compounds.

The arylazopyrazoles and pyrazolin-5-ones have been synthesised in two stages (Scheme 1). Compounds in the first stage were synthesised by the coupling of sulpha drug with acetylacetone or ethylacetoacetate. In the second stage, arylazopyrazoles and pyrazolin-5-ones were prepared by the reaction of thiosemicarbazide with the coupled products of acetylacetone and ethyl acetoacetate respectively. Structures of the compounds have been established on the basis of elemental and spectral analyses. The reactivity of diazonium salt of sulphonamides in stage-I and that of the coupled products with thiosemicarbazide in the stage-II was smooth and the products were obtained in good yields.

Experimental

Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Carl-Zeiss spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Varian 270 MHz using TMS as an internal standard. All melting points are uncorrected. Compounds were routinely checked for their purity on silica gel-G tlc plates.

1-Thiocarbamoyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-sulphonamoylazo-pyrazole (1): The starting reagent 3-sulphonamoylhydrazonopentane 2,4-dione required for the synthesis was prepared as follows. Sulphanilamide (0.01 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of concentrated HCl (4 ml) and water (5 ml) and cooled to 0° in an ice-bath. To it, a cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.69 g) was then added. The diazonium salt so obtained was filtered into a cooled mixture of sodium acetate (10 g) and pentane-2,4-dione (0.01 mol) in ethanol. The resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised to give 3-sulphonamoylhydrazonopentane-2,4-dione (65%), m.p. 205° (Found: C, 46.52; H, 4.32; N, 14.6. C₁₁H₁₃N₃O₄S calcd. for: C, 46.64; H, 4.59; N, 14.84%; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 260 (NH), 1 670 (CO involved in hydrogen bonding), 1 130 (SO₂), 1 525 (NH-N=C) and 1 750 cm⁻¹ (substituted phenyl); δ 2.5 (3H, CH₃), 2.67 (OCH₃), 3.6 (2H, NH₂) 7.4–8.4

Scheme 1. Reagents: (i) CH₃COCH₂COCH₃, CH₃COONa, (ii) CH₃COCH₂COOC₂H₅, CH₃COONa, (iii) NH₂CSNHNH₂, CH₃COOH.

(substituted phenyl) and 13.6 (¹H, NH hydrogen bonded). Similarly other diones were prepared (Table 1).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 1-4*

Compd. no.	M.p.* °C	Yield %	Colour	Molecular** formula
1a	205	65	Yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ S
1b	243	68	Yellow	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ S
1c	168	70	Brown	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S
1d	183	62	Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S
1e	165	55	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S
1f	222	60	Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S
1g	175	60	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S
1h	166	52	Yellow	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ S
1i	88	45	Brown	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S
1j	220	55	Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S
1k	227	62	Yellow	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄ S
2a	172	72	Yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₄ S
2b	160	68	Orange	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₄ S
2c	141	70	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ N ₄ O ₄ S
2d	60	62	Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₇ S
2e	156	68	Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₆ S
2f	142	65	Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₇ S
2g	71	58	Brown	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₆ S
2h	137	55	Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₆ S
3a	210	42	Yellow	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂
3b	113	45	Yellow	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂
3c	112	42	Yellow	C ₁₅ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂
3d	108	40	Yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂
4a	181	52	Yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂
4b	150	45	Pale	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂
4c	197	48	Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂
4d	193	55	Yellow	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

To 3-sulphonamoylhydrazonopentane-2,4-dione (0.002 mol) dissolved in acetic acid (15 ml), a solution of thiosemicarbazide (0.002 mol) in acetic acid was added and the mixture was refluxed for about 6 h and then the mixture was allowed to stand overnight. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol, (52%), m.p. 210° (Found: C, 42.30; H, 4.29; N, 24.61. C₁₂H₁₄N₄O₂S₂ calcd. for: C, 42.60; H, 4.14; N, 24.85%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 210 (NH), 1 630 (C=C or C=N), 1 490 (N=N), 750 (phenyl) and 1 140 cm⁻¹ (SO₂); δ 2.60 (6H, CH₃), 3.3 (2H, NH₂) and 7.1–8.1 (H, substituted phenyl). Similarly, the other arylazopyrazoles were prepared (Table 1).

1-Thiocarbamoyl-4-sulphonamoylhydrazono-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (2): The starting reagent 2-sulphonamoylhydrazonobutyrate-1,3-dione was synthesised by the method similar to that adopted for 3-sulphonamoylhydrazonopentane-2,4-dione except that ethyl acetoacetate was used in place of pentane-2,4-dione for coupling the diazonium salt of sulpha drug. The resulting solid was washed with water and recrystallised to give 2-sulphonamoylhydrazonobutyrate-1,3-dione, (70%), m.p. 172° (Found: C, 43.71; H, 4.54; N, 20.21. C₁₃H₁₇N₄O₆S calcd. for: C, 43.94; H, 4.78; N, 19.72%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 310 (NH), 1 670 (CO), 1 750 (CO involved in hydrogen bonding) and 1 110 (SO₂); δ (DMSO-d₆) 2.52 (3H, COCH₃), 1.36 (3H, COOCH₂CH₃), 4.32 (2H, COOCH₂), 14.70 (NH) and 7.30–8.10 (substituted phenyl). Similarly, other diones were prepared (Table 1).

A solution of thiosemicarbazide (0.002 mol) in acetic acid was added to the mixture of 2-sulphonamoylhydrazonobutyrate-1,3-dione (0.002 mol) in

acetic acid (15 ml) and the mixture refluxed for 6 h. It was then cooled and allowed to stand overnight. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give 1-thiocarbamoyl-4-sulphonamoylhydrazono-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one, (55%), m.p. 181° (Found: C, 37.42; H, 3.36; N, 29.12. C₁₂H₁₄N₄O₂S₂ calcd. for: C, 37.69; H, 3.66; N, 29.32%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 230 (NH), 1 710 (CO), 1 525 (NH–N=C), 750 (substituted phenyl) and 1 120 cm⁻¹ (SO₂); δ 2.5 (3H, CH₃), 7.0–8.0 (substituted phenyl) and 11.6 (H, NH). Similarly, other pyrazolin-5-ones were prepared (Table 1).

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